

PROGRESS & PROMISE IN DISCONTINUOUSLY REINFORCED ALUMINUM

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INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced aluminum metal matrix composites comprise a technologically maturing materials system capable of competing with conventional aluminum and titanium alloys, and organic matrix composites. For many years, metal matrix composites (MMC's) have been a promising, and often-promised, structural materials solution. Recent successes embodied in the Defense Production Act Title III Program on Discontinuously Reinforced Aluminum (DRA) demonstrate that the investment and diligence of the composites community is starting to pay off in significant production volumes and high-visibility component applications. This article discusses the technological development of DRA, the lessons learned about materials insertion from the Title III Program, and the recently launched Aluminum MMC Consortium.

DRA is an aluminum metal matrix composite where the reinforcement is a particulate, flake, whisker, or short fiber, typically of a strong, stiff ceramic material. DRA is a highly versatile engineering material with a unique combination of strength, stiffness, and affordability, as well as the ability to be processed and finished using conventional metal processing. It also has good wear and corrosion resistance, and can also be anodized. DRA Technology has matured to the point where components are now being produced for aircraft structures, gas turbine engines, automobiles, electronics, spacecraft and recreational goods.

ABSTRACT

A number of recent successful applications of DRA will be discussed. The first, the F-16 Falcon's ventral fins (see figure 1) provide lateral stability during high angle of attack maneuvers. They were originally made from aluminum alloy sheets bonded to honeycomb cores. The low stiffness of the aluminum skins combined with in-flight buffeting caused the ventral fins to fail after only 400 hours on average — sometimes shearing off in flight. DRA, because it offers 40% increased stiffness over aluminum at essentially the same density, was a good candidate to reduce the deflections. Ogden Air Logistics Center, the F-16 Systems Program Office, and Lockheed redesigned and qualified an improved ventral fin incorporating DRA sheet skins and an improved leading edge. The DRA ventral fin is projected to last over 6000 flight hours, and is now a preferred spare for all older USAF, Reserve, and Air National Guard F-16s. It is expected to save the Air Force approximately \$21 million in life cycle costs.

Ventral Fin

Fig. 1: F-16 Ventral Fin Images: Left, F-16 in flight. Upper right, failed ventral fin with aluminum skin. Lower right, improved DRA ventral fin.

Another success story from the Title III program was the fan exit guide vane component in the Pratt & Whitney 4000 series gas turbine engines. These high-thrust engines power many of the Boeing 777 commercial airliners (see figure 2). The Fan Exit Guide Vanes (FEGV's) are located in the bypass section behind the fan. They improve thrust and engine efficiency by straightening swirl produced by the fan. FEGV's on previous engines were made from organic matrix composites, and had poor resistance to erosion (by rain, dirt, etc.) and foreign object damage (e.g. hail, stones, bird strikes: see figure 2). This led to poor damage tolerance and frequent replacement. Also, the cost of materials and labor to manufacture the composite made the acquisition cost high. Pratt & Whitney and the Title III Team were able to qualify an FEGV made from DRA as the only bill-of-material for all of their 90,000-lb thrust class engines. This technological success is even more significant considering the difficulty of producing the complex double-hollow extrusion to aerospace tolerances. Pratt & Whitney has quoted an acquisition cost savings of \$100 million over 10 years; the figure for life cycle cost savings is approximately twice as much.

Fan Exit Guide Vanes

Fig. 2: P&W Fan Exit Guide Vanes: Upper left, Boeing 777 commercial airliner. Lower left, P&W 4084 Engine with fan removed, showing guide vanes. Results of foreign object damage test: Upper right, lightly damaged DRA vane. Lower right, heavily damaged organic matrix composite vane.